

recommended for cold temperate region. Khumal 2 and Khumal 4 were selected for warm temperate regions under irrigation. Chaite 2 and Chaite 4 are

recommended for early season (Feb to Jun) and Barkhe 2 and Khajura 2 for normal season (Jun to Oct) cultivation under irrigation in tropical or

subtropical regions. Makwanpur 1 is released for rainfed lowland and Ghaiya 2 for rainfed lowland for the hot region. □

Evaluation of African Upland Rice Advanced Trial (AURAT) at Ibadan, Nigeria

P. G. Pillai, National Cereals Research Institute, Ibadan Sub-Station, P.M.B. 5042, Ibadan, Nigeria

Nurseries of 17 entries in 1985 and 15 each in 1986 and 1987 were laid out during the wet season at Ibadan in a

randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Plot size was 12 m². Four to six dry seeds were dibbled at 25 × 25-cm spacing.

Eleven entries were tested over 3 yr. In 1985, moisture stress reduced plant height and grain yield. IRAT104, which possessed clean grains, significantly outyielded the check FARO 11. Yields in 1986 were variable but not significantly different. In 1987, plant

height, tillering, and grain yields generally increased because of steady rainfall throughout the growing season. ITA305, ITA3 15, IRAT170, and UPLRi-5 yielded significantly higher than FARO 11.

Four entries—ITA305, IRAT161, IRAT 104, and ITA3 15—that outyielded FARO 11 by 25% were selected for national multilocation trials. □

Data management and computer modeling

Models for panicle growth simulation

G. F. Li and D. Senadhira, Plant Breeding Department, IRRRI

Panicle growth simulation helps determine rate and duration of grain

filling. Using data from 1987 wet season experiments at IRRRI, we tested six growth models to find the best one for simulating panicle growth.

Richard's function performed best, with the largest regression coefficient between simulated and actual growth. Logistic function ranked second,

followed by cubic polynomial, quadratic polynomial, negative exponential, and Gompertz function. Results indicate Gompertz function is not suitable for panicle growth simulation. □

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Effect of soil type on draft force needed to plow soils of South Sulawesi, Indonesia

T. M. Lando and B. Abidin, Agricultural Engineering Department, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops, P. O. Box 173, Ujung Pandang, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

We measured the draft required to pull special-purpose plows on different soils in South Sulawesi. Draft was measured with a drawbar dynamometer, three times for each soil. Carabao, cow, or human power was used, depending on site condition. Cuts were 15 cm wide

Draft of soil types in South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Soil	Soil draft (kN)			
	Wetland		Dryland	
	Grassy	Nongrassy	Grassy	Nongrassy
Grey alluvial	0.53	0.45	0.58	0.50
Old grey alluvial	0.66	0.51	0.63	0.57
Grey brownish alluvial	0.54	0.47	0.60	0.49
Yellowish grey alluvial	0.43	0.39	0.49	0.42
Hydromorphic alluvial	0.65	0.93	0.63	0.64
Brownish grey alluvial	0.54	0.46	0.65	0.59
Brownish alluvial	0.60	0.46	0.63	0.54
Complex brown Regosol, Mediterranean, and Latosol	0.44	0.40	0.48	0.37
Latosol	0.47	0.44	0.60	0.47
Reddish brown Mediterranean	0.52	0.47	0.57	0.51
Complex reddish brown Mediterranean and Latosol	0.56	0.50	0.57	0.51

Continued on next page